

ABSTRACT

As increasing demand and using of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRPs) in recent years, the necessity of recycling CFRPs has been also increased. Several recycling methods have been conducted such as retrieving carbon fibers in CFRPs. Pyrolysis and solvolysis are mainly used for retrieving carbon fibers. These methods, however, consume tremendous energy. In this study, mechanical recycling was suggested to recycle end-of-life CFRPs rather than retrieving carbon fibers for more efficient recycling. The material used in this research was carbon fiber/low melting-polyaryletherketone (CF/LM-PAEK) which has high thermal properties. Trimmed or end-of-life CFRPs were prepared to be used as materials of compression molding by crashing machine. In this step, crashed CFRPs flakes had large distribution of their sizes so that a shaker with sieves was used to normalize the size of flakes. Different aperture sizes of sieves were used for analyzing flake size effects on recycled CFRPs' mechanical properties. Compression molding was conducted by using heating press for recrystallizing polymers. Process parameters including temperature, pressure, cycle time and cooling rate were optimized using thermal analysis like differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). To find out the effect of sieving process, particle size distribution (PSD) was analyzed by image analysis and statistical analysis. To verify the quality of the recycled composites, cross-section of the recycled composites was observed through couples of processes including sampling and optical microscopy. It was observed that smaller flakes filled vacant space between bigger flakes which makes recycled composites less variance. To analyze mechanical properties of recycled CFRPs, tensile testing and flexural testing were conducted by differing weight fraction of bigger and smaller flakes. As increase of bigger flakes fraction, properties increased but standard deviation decreased. Also, fracture mechanisms were classified by observing in naked eye and measuring crack length. As increase of bigger flakes, delamination was dominantly occurred which makes composites weaker.

BACKGROUND

- Increase of demand for CFRPs
- Waste problems issued and **necessity of recycling CFRPs** increased
- Methods of recycling CFRPs: retrieving carbon fibers (pyrolysis, solvolysis)
 - high energy consumption, subordinate problems like environmental and human health problems
- **Mechanical recycling**: one of alternatives, less energy consumption

- Weakness of mechanical recycling: low mechanical properties, low reliability of recycled composites because of breakage of fibers and non-aligned fiber orientation
- Ways to overcome
 - 1) sieving for obtaining longer fibers
 - 2) measuring fiber length and orientation for prediction

MATERIALS

- UD tape laminated composites (carbon fibers/polyaryletherketone)
 - Crashing machine: 15mm-blade width, 550RPM-rotation, 7.5kW-motor
 - Sieving shaker: 300RPM, 2 min with 200g at once

EXPERIMENTS

Measurement of flake area (Image analysis using Matlab image processing toolbox)

1. Converting RGB image to binary with removing small pixels (powder), filling in boundary
2. Tracking boundary, summing pixels in boundary
3. Comparing background area to calculate flake area
4. Drawing histogram using calculated area data

Manufacturing of recycled composites

- Compression molding: 320 °C, 7 MPa, 30 min → heating and pressing for recrystallizing
- Cooling rate: 15 °C/min, 2 °C/min → understanding the effect of cooling rate on crystallinity
- Weight fraction of bigger and smaller: control group, experimental group (25% difference)

Mechanical test

- Sampling: waterjet cutting for making specimens
- Tensile test: ASTM D3039, 2 mm/min of crosshead speed, 50 mm of gage length
- Flexural test: ASTM D790, 5 mm/min of crosshead speed, 32:1 of span length to thickness ratio

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Flake area distribution

- Histogram of sieved flakes area: following Weibull distribution*
- Bigger flake: 170-scale, 1.999-shape parameter, smaller flake: 52-scale, 2.196-shape parameter
- Able to obtain indirect, direct **fiber length** information** by using easier method (**image analysis**)
- * Weibull distribution: one of 2-parameter continuous probability distribution, shape and scale parameters
- ** Known that: fiber length distribution of discontinuous fiber-reinforced composites following Weibull distribution

Mechanical properties

- Increase of bigger flake weight fraction: strength and modulus **increased by more longer fibers in bigger flakes**
- Role of smaller flake: **variation decreased** by filled vacant spaces
- Less effect of longer fibers on flexural properties: because of flexural test under combination of several load (shear, compression, tension)

Correlation between fracture modes and flexural strength

- Flexural specimen: under combination of several loads → various fracture modes by complex loads
- Division of fracture modes: fracture length ratio of plane to thickness direction (horizontal to vertical length ratio in red triangle)
- Increase of bigger flake: increase of fracture length ratio → **inducing delamination** by bigger flakes
- Flexural strength trend: except case 4 and 5, through thickness fracture > delamination
- Combination of two effects: longer fibers effect > delamination effect in **case 4 and 5** → overtaking
- Variation of strength value: delamination > through thickness → **catastrophic failure** in delamination

CONCLUSIONS

1. It was confirmed that area distribution of sieved flakes follows Weibull distribution by image analysis.
2. Manufacturing process of reCFRP was optimized with thermal analysis results by mechanical recycling.
3. Effects of flake area on mechanical properties and fracture mechanisms were investigated by controlling weight fraction of different sizes of flakes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was supported by "Overseas order-linked aviation parts industry process technology development in 2019" of the Korea Institute for Advancement of Technology (KIAT), granted financial resource from the Ministry of Trade, Industry & Energy, Republic of Korea.